

Resolution of Rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium Complexes into Their Optical Isomers

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Rhodium(III) tris-biguanidinium chloride has been resolved into its optical isomers by fractional crystallisation of the diastereoisomer, rhodium tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate. Unlike diastereoisomer, cobalt(III) tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate, this rhodium analogue does not exhibit any "asymmetric transformation of the second order". The *laevo-gyrate* forms the less soluble variety and separates first. The (-) and (+) enantiomers of the complex chloro(+)-tartrate, (-)-chloride, and (-)-nitrate have been obtained in a pure state and their optical rotations have been measured. The molecular rotation of rhodium(III) tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = \pm 951^\circ$, is much less than that of the corresponding cobalt complex, viz., $[\alpha]_D^{25} = \pm 2153^\circ$.

The optically active rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium salts show no tendency of racemisation on keeping for years or in aqueous solution. Different anions and cations have no effect on their inertness and the racemisation could not be effected even by boiling an aqueous solution of the complex chloride with activated charcoal.

Biguanide acts as a bidentate chelate, forming inner-metallic complex salts of the second order'. With trivalent ions, like Cr(III) and Co(III), it forms octahedral complexes. The tris-biguanidinium complexes, like tris-ethylenediamine complexes, do not have any centre or plane of symmetry and are potentially resolvable into their optical isomers. The Cr(III)-tris-biguanidinium complexes could not be resolved due to rapid hydrolysis of their aqueous solutions. The cobalt(III) complexes, being more stable, have been resolved by Ray and Dutta. A very interesting phenomenon of 'asymmetric transformation of the second order', claimed to be the first of its kind in inorganic chemistry, was observed during the fractional crystallisation of the diastereoisomers, cobalt(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate.

Rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium complexes³ resemble the corresponding Co(III) complexes very closely in their physical and chemical properties. These are also octahedral and very stable and hence present a suitable case for stereochemical studies, specially in view of exhibition of the phenomenon of "asymmetric transformation of the second order" by the cobalt(III)-tris-biguanidinium complex. This communication describes the resolution of rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium complexes into optical enantiomers and a qualitative study of their optical stability.

Rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloride was resolved by forming diastereoisomer, (+)-rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate which was then fractionally

1. Ray *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1937, 14, 670.
2. *Ibid.*, 1941, 20, 289.
3. Sinha and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 179.

crystallised. The least soluble fractions are *laevo*-rotatory, as has been observed in the case of resolution of other complexes of rhodium by Werner⁴.

Incidentally, the *laevo*-rotatory cobalt(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate was also found to form the less soluble variety⁵, suggesting a correspondence in the configuration of the *laevo*-isomers of the Co(III)- and Rh(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrates. In the ethylenediamine series, however, the *dextro*-isomer of cobalt complex-(+)-tartrate and *laevo*-isomer of the rhodium complex-(+)-tartrate were found to be the less soluble forms.

On further fractionation, the rotation gradually diminished, finally reversing the sign. *Dextro*-isomers were thus readily obtained. We could not observe any asymmetric transformation as was reported in the case of cobalt(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate by Ray and Dutta².

The active complex, chloro(+)-tartrate, was converted into the relatively insoluble simple sulphates by double decomposition with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. The chlorides and nitrates of the two series were obtained from these sulphates.

The rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate and chloride have molecular rotations $[M]_D -951^\circ$ and -794° respectively. These values are much higher than those observed by Werner⁴ in the case of the corresponding rhodium tris-ethylenediamine salts, having $[M]_D -278.25^\circ$ and -347.6° respectively. This is attributed to the greater asymmetry of the rhodium-tris-biguanidinium complexes because though the biguanide molecule is symmetrically constituted like ethylenediamine, it, however, co-ordinates unsymmetrically.

The average molecular rotation of the rhodium-tris-biguanidinium complexes is also smaller than that for the corresponding cobalt complexes. This agrees with the observation of Jaeger³ that in the same series of complexes, the molecular rotations are inversely proportional to the atomic volume of the central metal ion.

Rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium complexes are extremely stable optically. A solid sample of (-)-rhodium-tris-biguanidinium chloro(+)-tartrate did not show any appreciable racemisation even after two years. The complex chloro(+)-tartrate could be heated to 120° without any loss in optical activity. It is also quite inert in aqueous solution. Several anions and cations were tested for their catalytic activity on the tendency of racemisation on the (-)-rhodium(III)-tris-biguanidinium complexes without any success. The racemisation could not be effected even on boiling an aqueous solution of the (-)-complex chloride with activated charcoal. This behaviour of the rhodium complex is in strong contrast to the easy racemisation of the active cobalt(III) tris-biguanidinium salts, observed by Ray and Dutta². This is probably due to the greater stability of the metal-ligand bonding in the case of rhodium(III) complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

(±)-Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium Chloro(+)-tartrate.—A solution of rhodium tris-biguanidinium chloride was treated with one molecular proportion of freshly prepared

4. Ber., 1912, 45, 1228.

5. Chem. Abs., 1920, 14, 1087.

ed silver(+)-tartrate, dissolved in water. The precipitated AgCl was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. A pale yellow residue was obtained which was analysed. {Found: Rh, 15.15; N, 31.20; Cl, 5.02; H₂O, 13.18. Calc. for [Rh(BigH⁺)₃] (+) Cl·C₄H₄O₆·5H₂O: Rh, 15.15; N, 30.96; Cl, 5.22; H₂O, 13.25%}.

(-)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium Chloro(+)-tartrate*.—The racemic salt, obtained above, was dissolved in the least quantity of water and slowly evaporated. The first crop of crystals separating was found *laevo*-rotatory which was fractionally crystallised till the two least soluble fractions showed the same rotation. The substance is quite stable optically. It becomes anhydrous at 120°, but the anhydrous salt shows optically activity in solution. A solid sample, kept at room temperature for over a year, did not show any appreciable change in rotation. An aqueous solution, left for 48 hours on a steam bath, also remained optically unaffected. {Found: Rh, 15.15. Calc. for [Rh (BigH⁺)₃] Cl·C₄H₄O₆·5H₂O: Rh; 15.15%}. For a 0.5% solution in water at 32±2°: α_D = -1.4°; [α]_D = -140°; [M]_D = -951°.

(+)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium Chloro(+)-tartrate*.—After separation of a few fractions of the *laevo*-gyrate in the above fractionation, the subsequent fractions showed very small rotations. When about half the dissolved amount had crystallised, the fraction became *dextro*-rotatory. This was further fractionated till two consecutive fractions showed the same rotation. (Found: Rh, 15.2. Calc. : Rh, 15.15%). For a 0.5% solution in water at 32±2°: α_D = +1.4°; [α]_D = +140°; [M]_D = +951°.

(-)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium Chloride*.—A solution of the (-)-chloro(+)-tartrate was treated with a saturated solution of (NH₄)₂SO₄ when the (-) rhodium-tris-biguanidinium sulphate precipitated. This was filtered, washed, recrystallised from hot water, and treated with the calculated amount of barium chloride. The filtrate from BaSO₄ was evaporated to dryness and analysed. {Found: Rh, 20.10. Calc. for [Rh (BigH⁺)₃] Cl₃: Rh, 20.08%}. For a 0.5% aqueous solution at 32±2°: α_D = -1.55°; [α]_D = -155°; [M]_D = -794°.

(+)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium chloride* was similarly prepared from the *dezero*-chloro(+)-tartrate. (Found: Rh, 20.08. Calc.: Rh, 20.08%). c=0.5%; α_D = +1.50°; [α]_D = +150°; [M]_D = +768.5°.

(-)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium nitrate* was obtained by metathesis of the *laevo*-sulphate and Ba(NO₃)₂. {Found: Rh, 17.55. Calc. for [Rh (BigH⁺)₃](NO₃)₃: Rh, 17.38%}. c=0.5%; α_D = -1.38°; [α]_D = -135°; [M]_D = -799°.

(+)-*Rhodium-tris-biguanidinium nitrate* was prepared similarly from the *dextro*-sulphate. (Found: Rh, 17.5. Calc.: Rh, 17.38%).

The following anions and cations in the form of different salts were added to different solutions and kept under conditions indicated in Table I. In no case any detectable racemisation was observed. A 0.4% solution of rhodium-tris-biguanidinium chloride was used.

TABLE I

Substance.	Conc.	Duration.	Temp.	Effect observed.
1. KCl	0.100M	24 hrs.	52°	No detectable change in rotation.
2. BaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	0.010	24	52°	
3. La(NO ₃) ₃	0.011	24	52°	
4. Ce(NO ₃) ₄ .NH ₄ NO ₃	0.005	24	52°	
5. Active charcoal	0.1 g./20 ml	10	Water bath	

The active charcoal used was freshly desiccated at about 400° in a covered crucible and cooled in a desiccator. The charcoal was added to the solution under investigation taken in a rubber-stoppered pyrex conical flask. It was then kept shaking in a thermostat at 50°±2° for 10 hours. The resulting solution was filtered and the filtrate examined polarimetrically.

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